

Preparation and Rearrangement of Alkyl and Allyl *N*-Arylformimidates

F. A. Hussein and S. Y. Kazandji

o-phenetidine, *o*-chloroaniline, *p*-chloroaniline, 2,5-xylylidine, 2,4-xylylidine have been condensed with ethyl orthoformate to furnish the corresponding formimidates(I). The latter have been rearranged to formanilides (II). Compounds of type (II) have been transformed to the secondary amines by acid hydrolysis and to tertiary amines by LiAlH_4 . Trans-esterification of (I) with allyl alcohol provides the corresponding allyl formimidates which are similarly rearranged, hydrolysed and reduced.

In the present investigation the authors extend the work of Merijan¹, and Roberts and Hussein². The amines used are *o*-phenetidine, *o*-chloroaniline, *p*-chloroaniline, 2,5-xylylidine, and 2,4-xylylidine. The first step in this reaction is the condensation of the amine with ethyl orthoformate to yield the corresponding formimidates (I). The latter compounds are rearranged to the corresponding formanilides (II). The main reactions carried out on the formanilides are the acid hydrolysis to provide the corresponding secondary amines (III), and LiAlH_4 reduction to furnish the corresponding tertiary amines (IV).

Trans-esterification of the formimidates (I) with allyl alcohol provides the corresponding allyl formimidates (V). Thermal rearrangement of (V) affords the corresponding allyl formanilides (VI). Incidentally, the acid-catalysed rearrangement was previously performed.² Chart-I illustrates the reactions investigated.

CHART I

(a) $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5$ (*o*)

(b) $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$ (*o*)

(c) $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{Cl}$ (*p*)

(d) $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ (2,5).

(e) $\text{Ar} = \text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$ (2,4).

1. M. Sc. Thesis, The University of Texas, June, 1957, p. 14.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 1950.

Two main types of reactions are carried out on the allyl formanilides (VI) viz. (a) The acid-hydrolysis to provide the corresponding secondary amines (VII) and (b) LiAlH_4 reduction to yield the corresponding methyl allyl arylamines (VIII).

As far as the mechanism of the rearrangement of the formimidates is concerned, that proposed by Chapman³ is considered to be very favourable.

The mechanism of the rearrangement of the allyl formimidate is similar to that proposed by Mumm and Moller⁴ for the rearrangement of allyl *N*-phenylbenzimidate to *N*-allylbenzanilide.

The mechanism of the reduction of the formanilide with LiAlH_4 clearly involves the cleavages of carbon-oxygen bond, i.e., hydrogenolysis, similar to the mechanism discussed by Gaylord⁵.

The IR spectra of the different compounds are in accordance with the structures proposed (cf. Tables I-VIII).

Furthermore, some of our compounds are known in the literature, namely:

N-ethyl-*o*-chloroaniline⁶⁻⁷, *N*-allyl-*o*-chloroaniline⁸, ethyl *N*-*p*-chlorophenylformimidate⁹, *N*-ethyl-*N*-formyl-*p*-chloroaniline⁹, *N*-ethyl-*p*-chloroaniline⁹⁻¹⁰, *N*-ethyl-2,5-xylylidine¹¹, *N*-ethyl-2,4-xylylidine^{9,10,12}, and *N*-allyl-2,4-xylylidine¹³.

EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points and boiling points are not corrected. The analysis was carried out by Alfred Bernhardt, Max Planck Institute, Mulheim, Ruhr, Germany. I.R. spectra were measured on Perkins-Elmer infracord Model 137 Spectrophotometer (pure liquids).

Ethyl N-Arylformimidates.—A mixture of freshly distilled substituted aniline (1*M*), ethyl orthoformate (1.5*M*), and HCl (0.5 g.) was placed in a 500-ml. r.b. flask, fitted with a 2 ft. glass helices packed column and a capillary tube. The flask was heated in an oil bath (90-115°), and the ethanol was removed from the reaction flask as soon as it was formed; 105-110 ml (theoretical 116 ml) ethanol was collected. The flask was allowed to cool to about 60° and the remaining liquid was fractionated under reduced pressure. (cf. Table I)

Allyl N-arylformimidates.—In a 250-ml. r.b. flask, fitted with a 2 ft. glass helices packed column and a capillary tube, was placed a mixture of ethyl *N*-arylformimidate (0.5*M*) and allyl alcohol (1 *M*). The reaction mixture was heated in an oil bath and the ethanol was removed from the reaction mixture as soon as it was formed; 25 ml (theoretical 30 ml) of ethanol, b.p. 78°, was collected. Excess of allyl alcohol was distilled at 98° and the remaining liquid was fractionated under reduced pressure (cf. Table II).

3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1743 (1927).

4. *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 2214.

5. Gaylord, "Reduction with Complex Metal Hydrides", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, p. 981, 1956.

6. Braun, *Ber.*, 1932, 63, 1578

7. Suter and Dains, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 50, 2737.

8. Lewis et al., *J. Org. Chem.* 1964, 29, 1183.

9. Roberts and Vogt, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 78, 4779.

10. Crowther, Mann and Purdie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, p. 65.

11. Heilborn and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", Vol. IV, p. 688, 1933.

12. Hickinbottom and Walne, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, p. 1558.

13. Wolf, *Ann. Chem.*, 1955, 592, 222.

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TABLE I

No. of Comp.	B.P./mm.	Yield ^d	<i>n</i> _D ²⁰	M.R.		Formula	Found	Reqd.	νC—H	νN=C
				Found	Calc.					
Ia	116°/4.9	61.1%	1.05	56.2	56.7	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	C: 67.88 H: 7.90 N: 7.53	68.98% 7.77 7.25	—	—
Ib	102°/4	65.5	1.15	50.0	49.7	C ₉ H ₁₀ ONCl	C:58.98 H: 5.65 N: 7.90	58.89 5.49 7.69	3.35	6.05
Ic	112°/4.9	70.0	1.177	50.2	49.7	C ₉ H ₁₀ ONCl Known Compound	Cl:19.49	19.28	3.35	6.12
Id	101°/4	73.4	0.978	54.5	54.06	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON	C:74.54 H: 8.36 N: 8.08	74.53 8.47 7.90	3.94	6.10
Ie	114°/5.5	70.0	0.981	54.5	54.1	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ ON	C:74.47 N: 8.45	74.59 8.47	3.35	6.05
							N: 8.11	7.90		

(Ic) identified by its refractive index.⁹

TABLE II

No. of Comp.	B.P./mm.	Yield	<i>n</i> _D ²⁰	M.R.		Formula	Found	Reqd.	νC—H	νN=C
				Found	Calc.					
Va	120°/3.5	64.7% ⁹	1.06	59.6	59.9	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N	C:70.05 H: 7.30 N: 7.01	70.24% 7.91 6.83	—	—
Vb	119°/4.8	69.2	1.16	53.52	53.1	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ONCl	C:61.53 H: 5.27 N: 7.91	61.36 5.15 7.16	3.30	6.05
Vc	111°/2.9	63.6	1.183	53.5	53.1	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ ONCl	C:61.16 H: 5.29 N: 7.34	61.36 5.15 7.16	3.32	6.06
Vd	103°/3.4	67.4	0.985	58.6	58.2	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON	C:75.60 H: 8.42 N: 7.61	75.60 7.93 7.40	3.90	6.05
Ve	117°/5	70.2	0.992	58.4	58.2	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ ON	O:75.43 H: 7.82 N: 7.21	75.60 7.93 7.40	3.35	6.04

Acid-catalysed Rearrangement of Ethyl N-Arylformimidates.—In a 100 ml. r.b. flask, fitted with a fractionating column and a capillary tube, was placed a mixture of the ethyl *N*-arylformimidate (0.123 *M*) and H₂SO₄ (conc., 0.004 *M*) and the flask heated on an oil bath. As soon as the inside temperature reached 170–80°, a vigorous reaction took place and the inside temperature jumped up to 200° while the bath temperature was still at 175°. The inside temperature of 175° was maintained for 30 minutes. The flask was then allowed to cool to about 60° and the remaining liquid was fractionated under reduced pressure (cf. Table III).

Thermal Rearrangement of Allyl N-Arylformimidates.—In a 200-ml. r.b. flask, fitted with a reflux condenser, was placed allyl *N*-arylformimidate (0.38 *M*). The flask was heated on a heating mantle at its boiling point for 3 hr. and then allowed to cool to about 60°. The liquid was fractionated under reduced pressure (Table IV),

TABLE III

No. of Comp.	B.P./mm	Yield	d_{20}^{20}	M.R.		Formula	Found	Reqd.	ν C—H	ν C=O
				Found	Calc					
IIa	150°/5	62.5%	1.09	54.69	54.86	$C_{11}H_{13}O_2N$	C:66.37 H: 7.78 N: 7.43	68.38% 7.77 7.25	3.35	5.90
IIb	134°/4	49.1	1.19	49.0	48.8	$C_9H_{10}ONCl$	C:58.40 H: 5.55 N: 7.29	58.83 5.49 7.63	3.34	5.92
IIc	135°/3.5	50.0	1.218	49.2	48.8	$C_9H_{10}ONCl$	Cl:19.23	19.28	3.40	5.95
IIc	122°/3.5	50.0	1.01	53.7	53.2	$C_{11}H_{13}ON$	C:74.44 H: 8.58 N: 8.00	74.53 8.47 7.90	3.30	5.93
IIc	122°/3	65.2	1.020	59.5	59.2	$C_{11}H_{13}ON$	C:74.99 H: 8.45 N: 8.15	74.53 8.47 7.90	3.30	5.92

(IIc) identified by its refractive index⁹

TABLE IV

No. of Comp.	B.P./mm	Yield	d_{20}^{20}	M.R.		Formula	Found	Reqd.	ν C—H	ν C=O
				Found	Calc					
VIa	168°/5	75%	1.08	58.98	59.01	$C_{12}H_{15}O_2N$	C:69.75% H: 7.65 N: 7.28	70.24% 7.91 6.83	3.38	5.93
VIb	131°/5	80	1.20	52.0	52.3	$C_{10}H_{10}ONCl$	C:61.23 H: 4.97 N: 7.42	61.36 5.15 7.16	3.34	5.95
VIc	144°/4.1	73.3	Solidified on cooling 71-73°C.			$C_{10}H_{10}ONCl$	C:61.36 H: 5.32 N: 7.30	61.36 5.15 7.16	3.20	5.90
VIc	135°/5	67.5	1.005	57.7	57.4	$C_{12}H_{15}ON$	C:76.01 H: 7.81 N: 7.61	75.60 7.93 7.40	3.35	5.98
VIc	129°/2.8	66.6	1.022	57.3	57.4	$C_{12}H_{15}ON$	C:76.10 H: 7.82 N: 7.74	75.60 7.93 7.40	3.35	5.98

N-Ethyl Arylamines.—A mixture of *N*-ethyl-*N*-formylarylamine (0.055 *M*) and 10% HCl was placed in a r.b. flask, fitted with a reflux condenser. The mixture was gently boiled for 2 hr. The resulting clear solution was allowed to cool to the room temperature, rendered alkaline with 10% NaOH solution, and extracted with ether (3×20 ml.). The combined extract after being dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate for 1 hr. was filtered, the solvent was evaporated and the remaining liquid distilled under reduced pressure (Table V).

N-Allylarylamine.—A mixture of *N*-allyl-*N*-formylarylamine (0.045 *M*) and 10% HCl (30 ml.) was placed in a r.b. flask and refluxed for 2 hr. The resulting clear solution was allowed to cool to the room temperature, made alkaline, extracted with ether (3×30 ml.) and dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate. The solution was filtered, the solvent evaporated, and the remaining liquid was distilled under reduced pressure (Table VI),

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TABLE V

No. of Comp.	B.P./mm	Yield	d_{20}°	M.R.		Formula	Found	Reqd.	$\nu_{\text{C-H}}$	$\mu_{\text{N-H}}$
				Found	Calc.					
IIIa	115°/3	77.9	1.032	50.3	50.7	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{ON}$	C: 72.94 H: 8.69 N: 8.22	72.72 9.09 8.48		
IIIb	214-16°	76.2	1.107	45.2	44.9	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{NCl}$				
IIIc	105°/2.9	89.5	1.143	44.9	44.7	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{10}\text{NCl}$			3.4	2.80
IIIId	221-24°	74.6	0.955	49.4	49.1	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}$				
IIIe	230-31°	76.1	0.945	49.3	49.1	$\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{13}\text{N}$				

(IIIb) identified by its density and as HCl salt derivative⁶⁻⁷.

(IIIc) identified by its boiling point and as *p*-toluenesulphonyl derivative⁹⁻¹⁰.

(IIIId) identified by its boiling point¹¹.

(IIIe) identified by its boiling point¹⁰⁻¹².

TABLE VI

No. of Comp.	B.P./mm	Yield	d_{20}°	M.R.		Formula	Found	Reqd.	$\nu_{\text{C-H}}$	$\mu_{\text{N-H}}$
				Found	Calc.					
VIIa	110°/2.2	88.2%	1.03	54.5	54.9	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{ON}$	C: 74.28% H: 8.93 N: 8.00	74.47% 8.46 7.89	—	—
VIIb	93-97°/1.5	80.0	1.178	48.1	48.1	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{NCl}$			3.50	2.82
VIIc	109°/2.9	72.3	1.145	48.6	48.1	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{10}\text{NCl}$	C: 64.36 H: 5.93 N: 8.55 Cl: 21.40	64.48 5.97 8.35 21.40		
VIIId	89°/3.2	76.7	0.960	53.5	53.3	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}$	C: 81.63 H: 9.10 N: 8.34	81.92 9.30 8.68	3.35 2.80	3.42 2.80
VIIe	111-13°/7	68.5	0.955	52.9	53.3	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{15}\text{N}$				

(VIIb) identified by its B.P.⁸.

(VIIc) identified by its refractive index¹³.

Reduction of N-Ethyl-N-formylarylamine.—A solution of LiAlH_4 (0.08 *M*) in THF (40 ml) was placed in a 250 ml. three-necked flask, fitted with a dropping funnel, a stirrer, and a reflux condenser. From the dropping funnel was added a solution of *N*-ethyl-*N*-formylarylamine (0.05 *M*) in THF (30 ml) dropwise so as to maintain a gentle reflux. When the addition was completed, the solution was refluxed for 2 hr., allowed to cool to the room temperature, and a few ml of ice-water were added in order to destroy excess of the reducing agent. The solution was made alkaline with a 10% solution of NaOH and the THF layer was separated. The aqueous layer was extracted with ether (3 × 25 ml). The combined ether extract was added to the THF layer and the resulting solution was dried over anhydrous potassium carbonate for 2 hr. The solution was filtered, the solvent evaporated, and the remaining liquid was distilled under reduced pressure (Table VII).

Reduction of N-Allyl-N-formylarylamine.—*N*-allyl-*N*-formylarylamine (0.04 *M*) in THF (25 ml) was similarly reduced dropwise as the preceding compound with a solution of LiAlH_4 (0.06 *M*) in THF (30 ml) and the resulting solution was refluxed for 2 hr. It was cooled. Subsequent procedures were the same as applied in the case of the preceding compound.

TABLE VII

No. of Comp.	B.P./mm	Yield	d ₂₀	M.R.		Formula	Found	Reqd
				Found	Calc.			
IVa	95°/2.9	59.7%	0.984	46.2	55.8	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ ON	C:73.13% H: 9.00 N: 7.42	73.63% 9.48 7.81
IVb	88.5°/ 4.9	67.6	1.101	49.5	49.1	C ₉ H ₁₂ NCI	C: 63.33 H: 6.81 N: 8.00 Cl:20.41	63.67 7.13 8.25 20.88
IVc	102°/2.9	75.0	1.138	49.0	49.1	C ₉ H ₁₄ NCI	C: 63.23 H: 7.25 N: 8.33	63.67 7.13 8.25
IVd	85°/3.2	62.3	0.927	54.1	54.2	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N	C: 80.62 H:10.03 N: 9.00	80.91 10.41 8.58

TABLE VIII

No. of Comp.	B.P./mm	Yield	d ₂₀	M.R.		Formula	Found	Reqd.
				Found	Calc.			
VIIIa	122°/30	64.0%	1.016	59.5	60.0	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ ON	C:75.62% H: 9.00 N: 7.50	75.81% 8.88 7.92
VIIIb	109°/5.0	70.7	1.125	52.8	53.2	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NCI	C:65.83 H: 6.42 N: 7.35 Cl:19.12	66.12 6.61 7.71 19.55
VIIIc	108°/2.9	76.0	1.13	53.1	53.2	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ NCI	C:65.83 H: 6.32 N: 7.43 Cl:19.3	66.12 6.61 7.71 19.55
VIIIId	84°/2.9	68.9	0.937	58.7	58.4	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ N	C:82.01 H: 9.45 N: 7.55	82.22 9.70 7.99

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